
BEE JP2: Neglect of natural healing capabilities—The unknown, forgotten, underestimated, and underutilized healing garden

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“To ensure the health of the prophet of the Bird Village, the disciples scrambled to make preparation: nutritious vegetables, mashed cornmeal, soft rice, herbs, etc.”

—In “No-fish Dietary”; *Wild Wise Weird* (2024)

[BEE JOINT PAPER]

1. Project description

For centuries, medicinal plants and herbal remedies have been integral to treating diseases and improving physical health. In 1773, an extraordinary experiment in Grenada—just off the coast of South America—highlighted this tradition. Alexander J. Alexander, a planter, conducted a groundbreaking study known as the slave cures of *Materia Medica*. This investigation evaluated remedies developed by Amerindians for a bacterial infection that caused severe ulcers and lesions on the hands and feet of enslaved individuals. These traditional cures laid the foundation for what we now

recognize as tropical medicine [1].

In recent years, environmental health has increasingly focused on toxicology and exposure science, driven by the rise of pollution-related hazards [2]. Yet, amidst modern challenges, there is growing interest in revisiting the therapeutic and health-enhancing effects of natural elements.

Photo: Natural Remedies (Copyright (c) 2016 Sebastian Duda/ Shutterstock)

Humans benefit from nature in various ways, whether through immersive experiences or interactions with single elements. Research suggests that coastal environments, for example, serve as therapeutic landscapes, offering restorative effects that promote better health and well-being [3,4]. Even short visits to the coast have been linked to improved physical and mental health [5].

However, frequent trips to coastal areas are not feasible for everyone. This raises the question: how can we bring nature's healing benefits closer to home?

For many, home gardens provide the most accessible connection to nature. Historically, these gardens were practical spaces for growing food and cultivating

medicinal plants to treat common illnesses. However, modern housing trends, including limited gardening spaces, have shifted the purpose of home gardens toward decorative and leisure functions [6].

Nature-based healing, deeply rooted in Indigenous health practices, remains underappreciated in contemporary healthcare systems [7]. These traditions, often forgotten or underestimated, hold valuable insights into addressing today's health and environmental challenges.

Drawing inspiration from the philosophical ideas in the “No-Fish Dietary” story featured in *Wild Wise Weird*, this commentary explores the untapped potential of home gardens as spaces for healing. As the world grapples with climate change and environmental degradation, reconnecting with the healing power of nature—starting with our own home gardens—offers a sustainable path forward [8,9].

2. Collaboration procedure

Portal users should follow these steps for registering to participate in this research project:

1. Create an account on the website (preferably using an institution email).
2. Comment your name, affiliation, and your desired role in the project below this post.
3. Patiently wait for the formal agreement on the project from the AISDL mentor/project coordinator.

If you have further inquiries, please contact us at aisdl_team@mindsponge.info

If you have been invited to join the project by an AISDL member, you are still encouraged to follow the above formal steps.

All the resources for conducting and writing the research manuscript will be distributed upon project participation.

Coordinator for this project: ***Ni Putu Wulan Purnama Sari***.

Mentor for this project: **Minh-Hoang Nguyen**.

The research project strictly adheres to scientific integrity standards, including authorship rights and obligations, without incurring an economic burden at participants' expenses.

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